

Study on Oscillatory Behavior and Dynamic Release of Alkaloids of Cultured *Catharanthus roseus* Cells

YU-MIN YANG, YING-JIN YUAN*, CHUN-MEI SHI and TSUNG-TING HU

Department of Chemical Engineering, Tianjin University, Tianjin, People's Republic of China

Manuscript received 16 January 1997, revised 7 August 1997, accepted 5 March 1998

During the growth of *Catharanthus roseus* cells, the extracellular pH, along with the both intracellular and extracellular alkaloid contents, oscillate under both long-term and short-term sampling. This study investigates the possibility of manipulating the extracellular pH to induce the release of intracellularly retained alkaloids. The results show that shifting the pH leads to a dynamic release of intracellular alkaloids of *C. roseus* cells, and meanwhile has no harmful effects on alkaloid synthesis of *C. roseus* cells. Lowering the pH can thus be an means to strengthen the release of intracellular alkaloids in large quantities.

Plant cell culture technology and its potential in secondary metabolite production is an important field of biotechnology¹. But more widespread application of this technology will require further progress in certain fundamental areas of plant cell culture. For example, most secondary metabolites are stored in cells rather than secreted into the medium. This produce both biological problems, inducing inhibition of biochemical reactions and catabolism of the secondary metabolites, and technological problems such as the low alkaloids content and the need to destroy the cells to recover product, both of which make continuous production of secondary metabolites impossible. Consequently, inducing the release of intracellularly retained products is essential to overcome the obstacle mentioned above and to make the producing process of secondary metabolite more feasible.

Some techniques have been used to obtain the release of products. For example, chemical agents² such as DMSO, toluene and nystistin have been used to permeate the cultured cells, which in turn lead to the release of intracellular products. Physical methods³ such as temperature, shock, laser and electroporation have also been used to alter the permeability of cultured cells to release the alkaloid. But sometimes both these methods lead to the disruption of cells. So to find a method that is more mild for releasing intracellular product is important. It is interesting that the alkaloids of *C. roseus* cells are naturally distributed between the medium and the cells, and the pH gradient⁴ across the plasmalemma of *C. roseus* cells has a great influence on the alkaloid distribution. Obviously, the secretion caused by the pH gradient⁵ is mild and the amount of alkaloid released is too small. To overcome the production problems outlined above, the process needs further investigation.

This paper deals with the changes in extracellular pH, extracellular and intracellular alkaloid contents during the

growth of *C. rosues* cells, examining both long-term and short-term behavior, in an attempt to enhance the release process of alkaloids of *C. roseus* cells by changing extracellular pH.

Results and Discussion

Oscillatory behavior of extracellular pH, extracellular and intracellular alkaloid contents during the growth :

During the growth in long-term : One day after cells were inoculated, the extracellular pH is approximately 6.3. It then drops to around 5.0, and finally oscillates between pH 5.0 and 5.5 (Fig. 1A). This result is consistent with that of Ganapathi and Karg⁶ who reported that pH usually increases to around 6.2 as a result of utilization of nitrate ions and then drops to around 5.0 as a result of utilization of ammonium ions during growth. The oscillatory behavior of extracellular pH reflects the regulating effects of the cells and the metabolism during metabolism variation during the growth.

Fig. 1. Changes in (A) extracellular pH, (B) intracellular and extracellular alkaloid contents during growth period : (●) extracellular pH, (○) intracellular alkaloid content, (△) extracellular alkaloid content, Ce.

Fig. 1B shows that after cell inoculation, the extracellular and intracellular alkaloid contents oscillate over time. Moreover, the lower pH values always correspond to the

higher extracellular alkaloid contents, which is consistent with ion-trapping model⁷. According to this model, alkaloids are low molecular weight amines whose neutral form is lipophilic and can freely diffuse through membranes. The alkaloids are synthesized in the cytosolic compartment and then diffuse through tonoplast to store in vacuole or through plasmalemma to retain in the medium, both in the form of non-diffusible cations. The cations are accumulated in vacuole or medium according to their pH and to the acidity constants of the alkaloids. So the equilibrium of intracellular and extracellular alkaloids is dependent upon the pH difference between the cells and the medium. But the oscillation in Fig. 1B indicates that alkaloids not only can be transported from inside to outside but also can be transported back into cells through plasmalemma or tonoplast by inversed concentration gradient. So active transport mechanism, in which alkaloids can be transported by carrier in the cell membrane through consuming energy according to Neumann and Zenk⁸, should also be involved in the alkaloid transport. To conclude, we think that alkaloids accumulate in vacuole or medium according to the pH difference between them and to the acidification of the alkaloids. They transport across cell membranes by simple diffusion and active transport simultaneously. Particularly, active transport mechanism is the dominant.

During the growth in short-term : The short-term effects were studied in both earlier exponential and later exponential phases, respectively. As shown in Figs. 2A and 3A, the extracellular pH oscillates in the range 5.0–5.5 during this phase, which is consistent with the pattern in Fig. 1A. The extracellular and intracellular alkaloid contents also oscillate in both the earlier and later exponential phases. Again the higher extracellular alkaloid contents always correspond to the lower pH extracellular values. We can thus conclude that the oscillations are intrinsic rhythms of cultured *C. roseus* cells, and they are the results of ion-trapping and active transport mechanisms taking effects simultaneously. Until now, few researchers have reported the alkaloid changes with time without changing environmental factors.

Fig 2. Changes in (A) extracellular pH, (B) intracellular and extracellular alkaloid contents in former exponential phase : (●, ○, Δ) have the same meaning as in Fig. 1.

Fig 3 Changes in (A) extracellular pH, (B) intracellular and extracellular alkaloid contents in later exponential phase (●, ○, Δ) have the same meaning as in Fig 1

Effects of pH perturbation on the release of alkaloid of cultured C. roseus :

Based on the experimental results and the analysis of the distribution of alkaloids between the cells and the medium as described above, one could expect that altering the extracellular pH would induce the release of intracellular alkaloids into the medium, and that such a release should be dynamic. The following experiments test the validity of this hypothesis.

Release of alkaloids by pH down-shift : Adding HCl lowers the extracellular pH to 3.2. Fig. 4 A and B show the resulting trends in extracellular pH, the intracellular and extracellular alkaloid contents. The extracellular pH rises gradually, while the intracellular alkaloid content first increases, then decreases, and then increases again. The gradual increase of pH indicates the regulating effect of the medium and the cells themselves. This result is consistent with that of Carbonell *et al.*⁹ who reported that the medium pH had to be adjusted every 12 h during the 5 days of treatment for one of the *C. roseus* hairy root lines. The first increase of intracellular alkaloid content results from the pH perturbation stimulating alkaloid synthesis or alkaloid accumulation as a defense against environmental to alkaloid synthesis or alkaloid accumulation as a means of defense against environmental changes⁸. The decrease of intracellular alkaloids results from the release of alkaloids into the medium. The extracellular alkaloid content exhibits oscillatory behavior, which can be caused by the pH gradient, the potential difference (caused by pH perturbation), and the change in membrane structure (caused by pH perturbation). The extracellular alkaloid content increases because of the acidification of the medium (Figs. 1–3). It decreases when part of the released alkaloids are again taken up by the cells once the potential difference changes⁵. The facts mentioned above indicate that the cells still have high alkaloid synthetic capacity and the maximum extracellular alkaloid content is greater than that shown in Figs. 1–3. So the release of alkaloids is strengthened by decreasing the pH, and a dynamic process is involved.

Fig. 4. Effects of pH shift down on release of intracellular alkaloids, initial pH 5.4. The cultured cells are in exponential phase; (●, ○, Δ) have the same meaning as in Fig. 1.

Fig. 5. Effects of pH shift up on release of intracellular alkaloids, initial pH 5.2. The cultured cells are in exponential phase; (●, ○, Δ) have the same meaning as in Fig. 1.

Release of alkaloids by pH up-shift : Adding NaOH raises the extracellular pH to 10.2. Fig. 5 shows the resulting trends in extracellular pH, and extracellular and intracellular alkaloid content. The extracellular pH decreases gradually, and extracellular and intracellular alkaloid contents oscillate. It may be noted however that the release of intracellular alkaloids is inhibited and the level of extracellular alkaloid is rather low.

Conclusion : The extracellular pH, intracellular and extracellular alkaloid contents all oscillate during the cultivation in both long-term and short-term. Raising or lowering the pH can induce the release of intracellularly retained alkaloids and can lead to a dynamic process due to the high activity of the cells. Lowering the pH of the medium can be an effective means of inducing release of intracellular alkaloids. Meanwhile it can be concluded that the ion-trapping model and active transport mechanisms contribute simultaneously to the distribution of alkaloids of cultured *C. roseus* cells between the cells and the medium.

Experimental

Cell suspension culture : Cell suspension cultures of *C. roseus* G. Don (Cell line CL-89) were grown in Murashige and Skoog (1962) medium supplemented with sucrose, 30 g/l, CH, 1g/l, biotin, 0.1 mg/l, 2,4-D, 0.5 mg/l, KT, 5 mg/l, VB₁, 10 mg/l, VB₆, 10 mg/l, before autoclaving (pH 5.8, temperature 26±2°). Suspension cultures were carried out on a rotary shaker at 100 rpm and subcultures were taken every 8 days.

Procedure : The cells taken for experiments were grown in culture medium (100 ml) in 500 ml Erlenmeyer flasks and cultured under conditions described above. During growth medium pH and cell alkaloid content and medium alkaloid content were measured in three growth modes : whole growth, early exponential growth phase and later exponential growth, with sampling intervals of 1 day, 4 h respectively. Medium pH was measured by a PHS-2 pH meter. Alkaloids were determined as reported¹⁰.

To test the effects of pH, NaOH was added to increase the pH and HCl was added to lower the pH during later exponential growth phase. Then, medium pH, cell alkaloid and medium alkaloid were measured at different time intervals.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge National Natural Science Foundation Committee of China and National Education Committee of China for financial support.

References

1. A. STAFFORD, P. MORRIS and M. W. FOWLER, *Enzyme Microbiol. Technol.*, 1985, 8, 578.
2. P. BRODELIUS, *Appl. Microbiol. Biotechnol.*, 1988, 27, 561.
3. H. TANAKA, C. HIRAO and H. SEMBA, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.*, 1985, 25, 890.
4. H. BOUYSSOU, A. PAREILLEUX and G. MARIGO, *Plant Cell Tissue Organ Cult.*, 1987, 10, 91.
5. Y. J. YUAN and Z. D. HU in "Collected Papers in Biotechnology", Chemical Industry Press, 1994, pp. 119-122.
6. B. GANAPATHI and F. KARG, *J. Exp. Bot.*, 1990, 41, 259.
7. J. P. RENAUDIN, S. C. BROWN and J. GURN in "Primary and Secondary Metabolism of Plant Cell Cultures", ed. B. NEUMANN, Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1985, pp. 124-132.
8. B. D. NEUMANN and M. H. ZENK, *Planta*, 1984, 162, 250.
9. L. A. S. CARBONELL, I. E. M. MENDOZA and O. M. VALENZULA, *Appl. Biochem. Biotechnol.*, 1993, 38, 257.
10. Y. J. YUAN, Thesis, Tianjin University, 1991.